

Food Science: A Primer

Matthew N. O. Sadiku¹, Tolulope J. Ashaolu², Sarhan M. Musa¹

¹Roy G. Perry College of Engineering, Prairie View A&M University, Prairie View, USA

²College of Food Science, Southwest University, Tiansheng Road Beibei District, Chongqing, China

How to cite this paper: Matthew N. O. Sadiku | Tolulope J. Ashaolu | Sarhan M. Musa "Food Science: A Primer" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-4, June 2019, pp.839-841, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23952.pdf>

IJTSRD23952

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

Food science has a hand in every product that is consumed. It provides us with frozen foods, canned foods, microwave meals, snacks, and variety of diets. Food science helps in feeding our ever growing population which is nearly 7 billion! It has evolved to make food the basis of a healthy civilization, help society overcome hunger and disease, and improve safety, affordability, and availability of foods.

COMPONENTS OF FOOD SCIENCE

Food science is multidisciplinary field, drawing from both pure and applied sciences. It combines chemistry, microbiology, physics, nutrition, and engineering. Other areas that food science embraces include agricultural science, sensory science, molecular thermodynamics, nanotechnology, and economics. Some of these areas are illustrated in Figure 1 [2]. Food science explores the nature of foods and focuses on the technical aspects of food. It covers all areas of food. Hence, food science covers several sub disciplines including the following [3,4]:

- Food chemistry is the study of chemical processes and interactions of all biological and non-biological components of foods. It examines food molecules in chemical reactions.
- Food engineering is the industrial processes used to manufacture food. It uses engineering concepts to solve problems in food manufacturing systems design and operations.

ABSTRACT

Food science is the discipline that applies basic sciences and engineering to study the nature of foods and their harvesting, processing, distribution, storage, and preparation. It is essential to meeting the needs of a growing global population. A major goal of food science is to understand the nature and properties of foods at a fundamental level so as to make existing food production processes more efficient. This paper provides a primer on food science.

Keywords: food science

INTRODUCTION

Food is a basic human necessity. The health and well-being of a nation depends on the ready availability of quality food at affordable price. The world population demands a sufficient and stable supply of nutritionally-balanced food. The increased reliance of society on ready-to-eat foods has led to greater responsibility for processors in terms of quality and safety. Tremendous progress has been achieved in recent years in the field of food production, processing, storage, and distribution. Food production have increased in most countries due to better production techniques and the introduction of Green Revolution [1].

Food science is the application of physical science and engineering principles to the creation and maintenance of a safe, abundant, and high quality food supply. It is applied science dedicated to the study of foods and how to transform food into a safe, convenient, nutritious, and healthy products.

- Food technology is the application of food science to the selection, preservation, processing, packaging, distribution, and use of safe food.
- Food microbiology is concerned with the study of the effects microbes or organisms can have on the quality and safety of food products. It also includes the study of the effect of the environment on food spoilage and food manufacturing.
- Food packaging looks at how food is packaged after processing to preserve maximum nutrients.
- Food processing, such as cooking and manufacturing, is concerned with preserving the safety and nutritious properties of food while allowing distribution to consumers.
- Food preservation involves the causes and prevention of food spoilage.
- Molecular gastronomy is a sub discipline of food science that seeks to investigate the physical and chemical transformations of ingredients that occur in cooking. It explore the physical changes that occur as food is prepared for human consumption.
- Food quality is the quality characteristics of food that are acceptable to consumers. When it comes to food, quality is an elusive term. Quality control also ensures that product meets specs to ensure the customer receives what they expect.

Some of these subdisciplines are illustrated in Figure 2 [5].

FOOD SCIENCE TOOLS

Food scientists have many excellent tools at their disposal with which to study foods and beverages (e.g. wine, tea, fruit juices). With the development of modern instruments, more and more tools are used in food science, including the following:

- **Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI):** When it comes to analyzing dynamic structural changes in food during processing and storage, no tool can compare with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). MRI food imaging techniques include gradient-echo imaging, functional imaging, whole plant functional imaging, flow imaging, and rheology [6].
- **Microscopy:** Knowledge of the microstructure of food materials is essential to predict and control their behavior. Light and electron microscopy have been widely applied to study all kinds of raw materials and processed products. The use of non-invasive imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is much restricted due to the elevated cost of the equipment. The atomic force microscope (AFM) is a member of the scanning probe microscopes family. The recent introduction of confocal scanning laser microscopy is a major advance in microscopy. It permits observation of selected levels within thick samples [7,8].
- **Spectroscopy:** There are several spectroscopic techniques depending on the different ways that atoms and molecules interact with electromagnetic waves. Mass spectrometry is used in food science, medicine, pharmacy, and botany. Raman spectroscopy analyzes the light dispersed by food material when it is illuminated by a laser source. It is a valuable tool in food materials science to interpret the mechanical, thermal, and rheological behavior of biomaterial. Researchers may use this tool as a complementary technique in the characterization of food microstructure [9].
- **Expert System:** This is a good instrument for information support of strategical and tactical manager decisions in different scientific and technological knowledge areas[10].

Internet resources and computerized surveys are frequently implemented as a developing tool to reproduce aspects of more sophisticated customer-research techniques.

BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES

Financial support of the food industry by the government is a indication of the significant role food plays in our society. The current availability, abundance, quality, and safety of food in most parts of the world is largely due to technological innovations in food production, supported by the food science discipline. Food science provides the foundation for the current quantity and high quality of foods [11].

Agricultural technology has favored large farmers and is not suitable for small farmers. Small farmers may lack technology that could be incorporated into the cropping system. In some cases, both producers and consumers have lacked knowledge of what constitutes good nutrition. Marketing and distribution of food are inefficient [12].

The needs of developing countries differ from those of the developed countries. Indiscriminate imposition of solutions

from outside to developing countries will not solve their problems.

Consumers are increasingly concerned about the origin of the environmental, societal, and ethical implications of their food choices. Deciding what to eat for dinner each night is hard, as food is connected to social, cultural, and economic circumstances. Overconsumption of affordable food (either at home or at restaurants) with high caloric value leads to obesity [13]. It is a major challenge for food scientists to give consumers guarantees that the food products are not only safe but produce better health.

CONCLUSION

Food science studies the preservation, selection, storage, and distribution of food. It is still a relatively new and growing discipline. In the future, food science will be called upon to address a number of challenges for mankind, including sustainability, nutrition security, longevity and health, and food safety and defense.

Since change is constant in food science, continuous learning should an essential activity of any food scientist who wants to remain current. Conferences, workshops, symposia, webinars, online programs, and short courses can provide a wide range of opportunities for professional development [12]. Cooperation among agencies involved in agriculture, nutrition, and food science is needed. Education on food science should be given emphasis at all levels of society in order to inculcate good eating habits in all age groups [14].

More information on food science can be found in numerous books in [6, 15-30] and the following journals exclusively devoted to it:

- Journal of Food Science
- Journal of Food Science & Technology
- Food Science & Nutrition
- Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture
- Food Science and Technology International
- Trends in Food Science & Technology
- Journal of Clinical Nutrition and Food Science
- Food Science and Technology International
- Trends in Food Science & Technology

REFERENCES

- [1] M. N. O. Sadiku, S. R. Nelatury, and S.M. Musa, "A primer on green revolution," *Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 5, no.7, 2018, pp. 332-335.
- [2] "Food science at Frankford School," <https://www.frankfordschool.org/Page/1328>
- [3] "Food science," Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Food_science
- [4] S. Gaffney, "Mapping the literature of food science revisited: 2003-2005," *Journal of Agricultural & Food Information*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2008, pp. 41-63.
- [5] Technological Educational Institute of Athens, http://www.teiath.gr/stetrod/food_technology/?lang=en
- [6] B. Hills, *Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Food Science*. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons, 1998.
- [7] M. Ferrando and W. E. L. Spiess, "Review: Confocal scanning laser microscopy. A powerful tool in food

science," *Food Science and Technology International*, vol. 6, no. 2, Apr 2000, pp. 267-284.

[8] B. Li et al., "Analytical capabilities of mass spectrometry imaging and its potential applications in food science," *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, vol. 47, 2016, pp. 50-63.

[9] A. Celedon and J. M. Aguilera, "Applications of microprobe Raman spectroscopy in food science," *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, vol. 8, no. 2, 2002, pp. 101-108.

[10] B. Makeeo and A. Zoueva, "Some APL defined functions for fast analysis of innovations in food science and human nutrition," *APL Quote Quad*, vol. 9, no. 4, June 1999, pp. 12-16.

[11] A. R. H., "Fischer, consumer behavior and food science," *Reference Module in Food Sciences*, 2016.

[12] P. S. Tong, "Food science education, research, and professional development," *Reference Module in Food Sciences*, 2016.

[13] D. J. Clements et al., "In defense of food science," *Gastronomica: The Journal of Food and Culture*, vol. 11, no. 2, 2011, pp.76-84.

[14] "Interfaces of agriculture, food science and nutrition," Unknown source.

[15] V. A. Vaclavik and E. W. Christian, *Essentials of Food Science*. Springer, 4th ed., 2008.

[16] B. Srilakshmi, *Food Science*. New Delhi, India: New Age International Publishers, 3rd ed., 2003.

[17] J. D. Ward and L. Ward, *Principles of Food Science*. Goodheart-Willcox Publishers, 4th ed., 2015.

[18] R. D. Hurt, *Agriculture and Food Sciences American Agriculture: A Brief History*. Ames, IA: Iowa State University Press, 1994.

[19] N. N. Potter, *Food Science*. Westport, CT: The Avi Publishing Company, 1968.

[20] M. Pyke, *Food Science and Technology*. London, UK: John Murray, 1964.

[21] M. Rothstein and D. Field (eds.), *Agriculture and Food Science: Quantitative Studies in Agrarian History*. Ames, IA: Iowa State University Press, 1994.

[22] B. A. Fox and A. C. Cameron, *Food Science: A Chemical Approach*. London, UK: University of London Press, 2nd ed., 1970.

[23] R. O. Morawicki, *Handbook of Sustainability for the Food Sciences*. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.

[24] A. I. Ihekoronye and P. O. Ngoddy, *Integrated Food Science and Technology for the Tropics*. London, UK: Macmillan Publishers, 1985.

[25] N. N. Potter and J. H. Hotchkiss, *Food Science*. New York: Springer Science & Business Media, 5th ed., 1998.

[26] Y. Ozaki, W. F. McClure, and A. A. Christy, *Near-infrared Spectroscopy in Food Science and Technology*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2007.

[27] The International Food Information Service (ed.), *Dictionary of Food Science and Technology*. Wiley-Blackwell, 2nd ed., 2009.

[28] K. T. Achaya, *Interfaces between Agriculture, Nutrition, and Food Science*. United Nations University Press, 1984.

[29] G. Campbell-Platt (ed.), *Food Science and Technology*. Oxford, UK: Wiley-Blackwell, 2009.

[30] R. R. Eitenmiller, L. Ye, and W. O. Landen, *Vitamin Analysis: For the Health and Food Sciences*. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group, 2nd ed., 2008.

[31] R. W. Hartel and C. P. Klawitter (eds.), *Careers in Food Science: From Undergraduate to Professional*. Springer, 2008.

Figure 1 Food science is a multidisciplinary field [2].

Figure2 Some subdisciplines of food science [5].